

Actions for Climate Transition
by developing
Future Aquaculture Strategies and Technologies

www.actfast-project.eu

Foreword

Dear stakeholders and colleagues,

I am delighted to introduce the first issue of the ActFast Newsletter, which will keep you regularly updated on our project's progress, activities, and results.

Since its launch, ActFast has commenced with remarkable energy and genuine enthusiasm across all partner institutions. Our diverse consortium, comprising leading research organizations, innovative companies, and dedicated aquaculture professionals, has demonstrated outstanding commitment to delivering tangible solutions for climate-resilient aquaculture.

What particularly encourages me is the remarkable interest that the project has already generated among stakeholders and the broader aquaculture community. The active participation of farmers, policymakers, and industry representatives affirms the relevance and urgency of the challenges we are addressing. This genuine enthusiasm validates that ActFast is responding to real, pressing needs in European and Mediterranean aquaculture.

This positive response motivates us to pursue our work with even greater dedication and rigor. We are determined to transform scientific innovation into practical solutions that will enhance the sustainability, productivity, and climate resilience of aquaculture operations across Europe and beyond.

Through this newsletter, we look forward to sharing our progress and keeping our extended network informed of exciting developments ahead.

Warm regards,

Prof. Alessio Bonaldo
Project Coordinator
Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna

The Project

Programme

Horizon Europe Innovation Action

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02

Duration

1 June 2025 – 31 May 2029 (48 months)

[Check out ActFast's website](#)

Our ambition

To develop and demonstrate climate change adaptation and mitigation solutions for European aquaculture, while supporting sustainable production and strengthening resilience across diverse aquaculture systems and regions.

The challenge: A Changing Climate

Across Europe, warmer waters are placing growing pressure on aquaculture systems, leading to stress, lower oxygen levels and more frequent harmful algal blooms. At the same time, pathogens and parasites can spread more easily, increasing disease risks, while invasive species are disrupting ecosystems and putting local production under additional strain.

A single mussel can filter up to **20** litres of seawater every day, helping keep coastal waters cleaner while producing nutritious seafood.

From Challenge to Action: Why ActFast?

We are joining forces to turn climate pressure into action by combining **science, technology, and practical sector knowledge**. Working across different regions and aquaculture systems, we aim to develop solutions that help farmers adapt, strengthen resilience, and move forward with greater confidence.

Four target regions

MEDITERRANEAN

Focus on seabass and seabream farms, highly vulnerable to heatwaves and disease outbreaks. Adaptive feeds and health solutions are tested in the Po Delta and other sites.

NORTH-EAST ATLANTIC

In Norway, salmon farming trials explore functional feeds and genetic tools to reduce gill disease and improve smolt quality.

RIVER DELTAS

In the Ebro Delta (Spain), Po Delta (Italy), and Nile Delta (Egypt), ActFast addresses mussel thermotolerance, combats invasive blue crab impacts on clams, and develops IMTA systems combining fish, shellfish, algae, and rice.

INLAND WATERS

In Hungary and Slovenia, carp, trout, and catfish farming demonstrations test wintering feeds, biosensors for pathogens, and duckweed-based IMTA to strengthen resilience in freshwater systems.

Objectives

1

Adapt

Develop climate-smart solutions for diverse aquaculture systems

2

Protect

Strengthen fish and shellfish health through resilient practices

3

Sustain

Support productive and sustainable growth under changing conditions

4

Improve

Promote circular, low-impact aquaculture approaches

5

Anticipate

Deliver early warning tools for climate-related risks

6

Empower

Share knowledge and skills across the sector

Did You Know?

Carp farming has been practiced in Europe for more than **1,000** years, making it one of the oldest forms of aquaculture.

Key innovations

AI-based Early Warning System

predicting climate threats for aquaculture (starting with the Mediterranean)

Smart Farming Systems

innovative, efficient, and climate-adapted production approaches

Fish Health & Welfare Tools

improved feeds, genetics, and monitoring to reduce disease and stress

*In **ACTFAST**, we are not working in isolation. We are bringing together different perspectives, from researchers to farmers, to better understand what is happening in the water and what it means in practice.*

We start by looking at climate risks across regions, then combine data, monitoring tools, and real-world experience to test solutions directly in aquaculture systems.

The goal is simple: to develop approaches that work not only in theory, but in everyday farming conditions.

The Virtual ActFast Lighthouse is the central showcase and training hub of the project: turning data, results and experience into a shared space where solutions can be explored, tested and shared.

Virtual Lighthouse

An immersive **VR training and demonstration platform** to explore climate risks, test adaptive solutions, and share best practices for climate-smart aquaculture

Pacific oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*) can change sex during their lifetime, often starting as males and later becoming females.

Impacts

The difference we aim to make

ACTFAST is designed to help European aquaculture move from reacting to climate pressure to being better prepared for it. Across the four target regions, we aim to support healthier stocks, smarter farming decisions and more resilient production systems, while also reducing environmental pressure and sharing practical solutions with the wider sector.

10%

lower mortality in seabass and carp

34,000 t

CO₂e/year potentially saved

€112M

potential avoided losses for Manila clam production in the Po Delta

€21M

extra retail-stage revenue for carp production in Central and Eastern Europe

Healthier stocks, fewer losses

We aim to improve survival and reduce health-related losses in key farmed species. The project targets a 10% reduction in mortality for seabass and carp, a 5% reduction for salmon, and a 10% cut in antibiotic and chemical use in European aquaculture.

More efficient production

ACTFAST also focuses on practical gains at farm level: 20% higher mussel productivity in the Ebro Delta, 20% less clam predation in the Po Delta, 5–7% higher seabass growth with 10% lower feed conversion, 5% better feed efficiency in salmon, and the elimination of winter weight loss in carp.

Lower footprint, stronger ecosystems

By improving feed efficiency and promoting circular approaches such as IMTA, we aim to reduce environmental impact as well as production risks. The project estimates that new Mediterranean feed formulations could save 34,000 tonnes of CO₂e per year, while wider uptake of delta solutions could help recover 520 hectares of salinised coastal land.

Knowledge that travels further

Beyond the farm, we want ACTFAST knowledge to reach the people who can use it. The project plans for 100 participants in courses, 800 webinar attendees, 500 users of the Virtual Lighthouse, and at least 100 stakeholders involved in engagement activities, alongside policy recommendations and outreach to decision-makers.

AquaFarm - Pordenone Fiere in Pordenone

We were pleased to present our two most relevant AI-based KERs during the session dedicated to new technologies in aquaculture and to meet many colleagues and stakeholders at our booth.

FEAP-GFCM: Technical Consultation on Sustainable Aquaculture Practices in Athens

ActFast presented 5/13 KERs of the project, it was particularly valuable in shaping a workshop focused on practical experience and operational needs.

BlueFeed Cluster Technical Webinar **From Science to Practice: Methodological Approaches within the BlueFeed Cluster**

Come see us at the next events!

18-21 May

XXII International Symposium on Fish Nutrition and Feeding

Darwin, Australia

28 Sep - 1 Oct

Aquaculture Europe 2026

Ljubljana, Slovenia

Visit us at the ActFast stand

Our team

We are a strong consortium of 31 partners joining forces across countries, disciplines, and sectors. Different backgrounds, shared ambition - together, we are shaping practical solutions for a smarter and more resilient aquaculture sector.

Sister project

We'd love to introduce you to our sister OCCAM!
Click on their logo to know more

Contact us

SUBSCRIBE

Stakeholder
survey

Project Coordinator

University of Bologna

Dr. Alessio Bonaldo

alessio.bonaldo@unibo.it

[ACTFAST LinkedIn](#)

[ACTFAST website](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union